

30 years of Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center

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Piotr Rydlichowski
Advances in Quantum Computing
and Communications

Quantum Technologies

Quantum Technologies

Quantum Technologies Timeline

1. Communication	2. Simulators	3. Sensors	4. Computers
0 – 5 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Core technology of quantum repeaters B Secure point-to-point quantum links 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Simulator of motion of electrons in materials B New algorithms for quantum simulators and networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Quantum sensors for niche applications (incl. gravity and magnetic sensors for health care, geosurvey and security) B More precise atomic clocks for synchronisation of future smart networks, incl. energy grids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Operation of a logical qubit protected by error correction or topologically B New algorithms for quantum computers C Small quantum processor executing technologically relevant algorithms
5 – 10 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> C Quantum networks between distant cities D Quantum credit cards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C Development and design of new complex materials D Versatile simulator of quantum magnetism and electricity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C Quantum sensors for larger volume applications including automotive, construction D Handheld quantum navigation devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D Solving chemistry and materials science problems with special purpose quantum computer > 100 physical qubit
> 10 years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> E Quantum repeaters with cryptography and eavesdropping detection F Secure Europe-wide internet merging quantum and classical communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E Simulators of quantum dynamics and chemical reaction mechanisms to support drug design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E Gravity imaging devices based on gravity sensors F Integrate quantum sensors with consumer applications including mobile devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E Integration of quantum circuit and cryogenic classical control hardware F General purpose quantum computers exceed computational power of classical computers

https://qt.eu/app/uploads/2018/04/93056_Quantum-Manifesto_WEB.pdf

Quantum Computing

Advancements and challenges

- Progress in terms of number and quality of qubits (inability to implement large enough problems)
- Different physical qubit implementation techniques proposed and tested
- Qubit readout errors require mitigation techniques
- Qubit logic, gates depth limitation
- Short coherence time
- New algorithms and techniques like VQE
- Control electronics
- Low speeds
- Integration with classical HPC - QPU

Quantum Computing

Current technologies for physical qubit implementation

- Superconducting qubits
- Ion traps
- Cold atoms
- Photons
- Defects in diamonds
- Silicon qubits (based on quantum dots or defects)
- Topological qubits
- ...

Quantum Computing

Superconducting qubits

Qubits: quantum states in nano electrical circuits

PROS:

- ns time for gate execution or readout
- low error level
- Ability to scale the technology using current CMOS technologies

CONS:

- low temperature for the processor < 20 mK
- Short coherence time

Currently 127 qubits, ~1000 planned till end of 2023

1Q typical gate time	~10ns
2Q typical gate time	~10ns – 100ns
1Q gate fidelity	up to ~99.9%
2Q gate fidelity	up to ~99%
Q coherence time	~50μs for capacitively shunted flux qubits and ~100μs for transmons
Coherence time/gate time	
Readout time	~100ns
Readout fidelity	~99%

Quantum Computing

Ion traps

Qubits: quantum states of ion in Pauli traps

PROS:

- Long coherence time (hundred of s)
- Low error rate
- Easy to achieve entangled states
- Ability to use technologies developed for atomic clocks
- Ability to work in room temperature

CONS:

- low speed for gate execution us

Currently ~20 qubits

1Q typical gate time	~1 μ s
2Q typical gate time	~1–100 μ s
1Q gate fidelity	up to 99.9999%
2Q gate fidelity	up to 99.9%
Q coherence time	from 0.2s in optical to ~600s for hyperfine Q
Readout time	~10 μ s
Readout fidelity	>99.99% in ~200 μ s detection time and 99.93% in 11 μ s
State preparation error	~2 \times 10 ⁻⁴

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Photons

Currently ~10-20 qumodes

Quantum Computing

Proposed scaling approach

<https://research.ibm.com/blog/ibm-quantum-roadmap-2025>

Quantum Computing

PRACE report

European start-ups and SMEs	Country	Quantum computing	Quantum software
Algorithmiq	Finland		Life sciences
Alice & Bob	France	Cat qubits	
AQT	Austria	Trapped ion qubits	
C12 Quantum Electronics	France	Carbon nanotube qubits	
Cambridge Quantum Computing	UK	Quantum compiler	Chemistry, ML, finance
CEA-Leti	France	Silicon qubits	
HQS Quantum Simulations	Germany		Materials science
IQM	Finland, Germany	Superconducting qubits	HW/SW co-design, finance, KQCircuits
Multiverse Computing	Spain		Finance
ORCA Quantum Computing	UK	Photonic qubits	
Oxford Ionics	UK	Trapped ion qubits	
Oxford Quantum Computing	UK	Superconducting qubits	
Pasqal	France	Rydberg atomic qubits	Pulser
Phasecraft	UK		Materials
Qilimanjaro	Spain	Quantum annealer	
Qu & Co	The Netherlands		Chemistry & materials
Quandela	France	Photonic qubits	
Quantastica	Finland, Estonia, Serbia	Quantum emulators	Programming tools
Quantum Motion	UK	Silicon spin qubits	
Qubit Pharmaceuticals	France		Pharmacology
Rahko	UK		Drug discovery
Riverlane	UK		Deltaflow.OS quantum computer operating system
Terra Quantum	Switzerland		Cybersecurity

Technology	QTRL	TRL	EU assets/players
Trapped ions	QTRL 5	TRL 6-7	AQT (10 qubits)
Neutral (Rydberg) Atoms	QTRL 5	TRL 6-7	Pasqal (100 [196] qubits)
Superconducting qubits	QTRL 5	TRL 5	IQM (5 - 20 qubits)
	QTRL 2	TRL 1	Alice&Bob
	QTRL 1-3	N/A	Oxford Quantum Circuits (4 qubits)
	QTRL 3-5	TRL 3-5	Qilimanjaro Quantum Tech (5 qubits)
Photonic qubits	QTRL 4	TRL 4	Quandela, Duality quantum Photonics, Quix (5-12 qubits)
CMOS silicon spin	QTRL 1-3	N/A	CEA LETI / CNRS

PSNC is Hosting a Quantum Machine as a part of EuroHPC

Selection of six sites to host the first European quantum computers

The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) has selected six sites across the European Union (EU) to host and operate the first EuroHPC quantum computers: Czechia, Germany, Spain, France, Italy, and Poland.

- R&D Purpose
- Available to EU users in scientific communities, industry and the public sector
- To help develop Q applications

https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/selection-six-sites-host-first-european-quantum-computers-2022-10-04_en

Quantum Computing

Quantum Communication

Implementations

- Closely connected with the development of other quantum technologies
- More advanced level of development and more practical use cases
- Quantum cryptography
- Quantum Key Distribution as practical implementation
- Single photon devices (sources and detectors)
- Limited reach and speed of transmission
- Lack of quantum memories for quantum repeaters
- A path toward quantum networks, quantum internet
- Way to connect quantum computers and teleport qubit data
- Entangled photon pairs required in great number and efficiently generated

Quantum Communication

Principles

Information can be encoded on properties of **single quantum particles** which can be found in **superposition** states

Photons are ideal carriers of quantum information
→ robust to ambient noise
→ can be transported over long distances

$$\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$$

with α, β complex numbers and

$$|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$$

Following the probabilities according to quantum mechanics, there is a non-zero probability of photon coming out!

Quantum Communication

EuroQCI and Digital Europe – start of projects

DECLARATION ON A QUANTUM COMMUNICATION INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE EU

24 Member States

have signed a declaration agreeing to **work together** to explore how to build a quantum communication infrastructure (QCI) across Europe, boosting European capabilities in quantum technologies, cybersecurity and industrial competitiveness.

The countries taking part in the initiative are Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.

@FutureTechEU #EuroQCI

A screenshot of the European Commission website. The page is titled "Shaping Europe's digital future" and features a navigation menu with links to Home, Policies, News, Library, Funding, Calendar, and Consultations. The main content area is titled "The Digital Europe Programme" and includes a search bar at the top right. The text on the page describes the Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) as a new EU funding programme focused on bringing digital technology to businesses, citizens and public administrations. It also mentions the European Commission's focus on a greener Europe and the Digital Europe Programme's role in supporting projects in five key capacity areas: supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, advanced digital skills, and ensuring a wide use of digital technologies across the economy and society. A large "30" graphic is overlaid on the right side of the screenshot.

Quantum Communication

EuroQCI and Digital Europe – start of projects

Figure 2: Overview of EuroQCI and its main elements

<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/euroqci-conops-concept-operations>

Quantum Communication

QKD Standardization

Quantum Communication Standardisation Roadmap (v2)

Quantum Communication

Quantum Networks Simulators

- QuISP, Keio/WIDE
- SimulaQron, TU Delft <http://www.simulaqron.org/>
- NetSquid, Dahlberg, TU Delft <https://netsquid.org/>
- SeQueNCe, Suchara, Argonne <https://cpb-us-w2.wpmucdn.com/voices.uchicago.edu/dist/0/2327/files/2019/11/SeQUeNCe.pdf>
- SQUANCH, Bartlett <https://pypi.org/project/SQUANCH/>
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.07047>
- QuNetSim, DiAdamo <https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.06397>
- QKD simulator in ns-3, including routing, Mehic et al <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8935373> <https://www.qkdnetstim.info/> <https://twitter.com/mickeyze2>
- Physical-layer, online calculator for SPDC <http://spdcalc.org/>
- QuISP - Quantum Internet Simulation Package https://aqua.sfc.wide.ad.jp/quisp_website/

Quantum Communication

Quantum Internet Research Group

- Document "Applications and Use Cases for the Quantum Internet" (draft-wang-qirg-quantum-internet-use-cases-06) during the last revision (end of May 2020).
- The document "Architectural Principles for a Quantum Internet" (draft-irtf-qirg-principles-03)
- The GÉANT WP6 T1 QKD Group submits its comments
- Abstract: "The Quantum Internet has the potential to improve Internet application functionality by incorporating quantum information technology into the infrastructure of the overall Internet. In this document, we provide an overview of some applications expected to be used on the Quantum Internet, and then categorize them using various classification schemes. Some general requirements for the Quantum Internet are also discussed. The intent of this document is to provide a common understanding and framework of applications and use cases for the Quantum Internet. "

Quantum Communication

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Wang, et al. Expires 11 September 2023 [Page 1]
Internet-Draft Quantum Internet Application Scenarios March 2023

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and how to provide feedback on it may be obtained at <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc9346>.

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Quantum Communication

New technologies – Long-haul QKD proof-of-concept

- Between 2 GÉANT PoPs (254 Km)
- A collaboration between GN4-3 (WP6, WP7), OpenQKD and Toshiba – coordinator GÉANT
- Based on a Twin Field Solution

Quantum Communication

New technologies

	Discrete variables	Continuous variables
Key encoding	Photon polarization, phase, time arrival	Electromagnetic field quadratures
Detection	Single-photon	Coherent (homodyne/heterodyne)
Post processing	Key readily available	Complex error correction
Security	General attacks, finite-size, side channels	General attacks, finite-size, side channels

BB84, Decoy state, Coherent One Way, Differential Phase Shift, (Measurement) device independent protocols

CV-QKD (one or two-way, Gaussian or discrete modulation, coherent or squeezed states, post selection), (Measurement) device independent protocols

V. Scarani et al, Rev. Mod. Phys. 2009
ED and A. Leverrier, Entropy 2015

Quantum Communication

New technologies – single atom quantum memory

Quantum Communication

Quantum Network Layers

- **Quantum Service Layer**
 - Quantum Entanglement Discovery And Distribution Service: e.g., Entangled Photonic Generation, Management, Distribution
- **Quantum Networking Layer**
 - SDN Control Functions, e.g., Wavelength Routing, Wavelength Assignment, Path Topology Creation Among Quantum Nodes, Related Devices
- **Quantum Link Layer**
 - Protocol Layer Manages Quantum signals and Messages Transmitted Through Quantum Channels Among Q-nodes, Monitors Quantum Link Status
- **Quantum Physical Layer**
 - Physical Connectivity (e.g., Optical Fiber)/Communication Among Quantum Nodes, Determines Quantum Channel Frequencies, Signal Rates, Photon Pulses Used For Quantum Signals et al

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